

graphia

GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

Work Package WP4

Artificial Intelligence Solutions for the SSH KG

Deliverable D4.3

Deployment of SSH LLMs

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Table of Contents

Deliverable Information	2
Change Log	2
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	6
List of Abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1. Purpose and Scope of the Document	9
1.2. Structure of the Document	10
2. Deployment Infrastructure	10
2.1. OKD Environment	12
Description	12
Architecture	13
OKD lifecycle	15
OKD in GRAPHIA	15
Monitoring and observability	16
Production readiness criteria for OKD-hosted services	16
2.2. HPC Environment	18
Inference Execution and Integration	19
Model Training and Fine-tuning	20
Scalability and Resource Allocation	21
Monitoring and observability	21
Production readiness criteria for HPC-hosted services	22
3. LLM4SSH models and related services: Current Deployment Status	24
3.1. LLM models for SSH	25
Service vllm-openai-mistral-24	25
Service Overview	25
Description	25

Service details	26
Service Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0	27
Service overview	27
Description	27
Service details	27
Service qwen-embedding-deployment	28
Service overview	28
Description	29
Service details	29
Service DeepSeek v3	30
Service overview	30
Description	30
Service details	30
3.2. LLM-related services	31
Service LiteLLM	31
OKD Microservices	31
Description	32
Service details	32
Service Quagga agent	34
OKD Microservices	34
Description	34
Service details	34
3.3. Performance and stress testing	36
3.4. Production-readiness status	37
4. Conclusions	38
4.1. Integration and Sustainability	38
4.2 Ethical and legal aspects	38
4.3 Final Remarks	39
Bibliography	40
Appendix A. Computing Infrastructure Resources Allocated to LLM4SSH	

List of Figures

Figure 1: Architecture of the GRAPHIA computing infrastructure deployed at PCSS, comprising OKD environments, HPC resources, and virtual machines.

Figure 2: Architecture of OKD

Figure 3: OKD Lifecycle

Figure 4: HPC Architecture

Figure 5: Distribution of requests across deployed LLM models over time

List of Tables

Table 2.1: Summary of the LLM services deployed within GRAPHIA and the mechanisms supporting their production readiness.

Table A.1: LLM4SSH resources allocated on OKD cluster bst2

Table A.2: LLM4SSH resources allocated on HPC infrastructure

List of Abbreviations

(v)CPU	(virtual) Central Processing Unit
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
LLM	Large Language Model
LLM4SSH	Large Language Models for Social Science and Humanities
OKD	Open Kubernetes Definition (free, community version of the Red Hat OpenShift)
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PCSS	Poznańskie Centrum Superkomputerowo-Sieciowe (Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center, former PSNC)

SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
vLLM	Virtual Large Language Model

Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to document the LLM services deployed within GRAPHIA and the infrastructure supporting their operation. As a software deliverable, D4.3 focuses on the operational characteristics of the deployed services, including their deployment environments, access mechanisms, ownership, and production readiness status.

This document provides an overview of the deployment architecture supporting GRAPHIA's SSH-oriented LLM ecosystem, spanning both OKD- and HPC-based execution environments. It describes the deployed LLM models, the services built upon them, and the operational infrastructure that enables their integration with GRAPHIA applications, pilot activities, and AI-enabled functionalities.

The deployment landscape described in this document should be understood as a snapshot of the operational state of the GRAPHIA SSH LLM ecosystem at the time of writing. At the time of submission, the deployed services are operational and available to their intended users. As the project progresses, both the underlying models and the portfolio of services built upon them are expected to evolve in response to technological advances and the needs of the GRAPHIA community.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Scope of the Document

This deliverable documents the deployment and operational aspects of the Large Language Model (LLM) ecosystem established within Task 4.1 of the GRAPHIA project. Task 4.1 focuses on deploying AI capabilities to support research and operational activities in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain. The deployed components can be grouped into two complementary categories. The first category comprises foundation LLMs hosted within the GRAPHIA infrastructure, providing reusable AI capabilities for inference and experimentation. The training and adaptation of these models have been described previously in Deliverable D4.1¹ and are therefore not repeated here. This deliverable focuses instead on their operational deployment and availability.

The second category consists of application-level services built on top of these models. These services expose concrete functionality to end users and other GRAPHIA components, including conversational interfaces, knowledge-graph question-answering workflows, and other AI-assisted tools that support SSH research activities. An overview of the GRAPHIA vision and its approach to combining knowledge graphs and AI for SSH research has been presented elsewhere (Romanello et al., 2025), while the use of large language models as an interface for exploring SSH knowledge graphs has been discussed by (Romanello, 2025).

Due to their heterogeneous computational and operational requirements, these components are deployed using complementary execution environments operated by PCSS. Containerised services are hosted on an OKD/Kubernetes platform, providing orchestration, scalability, and lifecycle management capabilities, while computationally demanding workloads leverage High Performance Computing (HPC) resources supporting LLM inference, experimentation, and model adaptation activities. The deployment architecture described in this deliverable follows the broader technical architecture of GRAPHIA presented in Deliverable D2.2 (De Santis et al., 2026)

The purpose of this deliverable is to document the operational deployment status of the GRAPHIA SSH LLM ecosystem at the time of submission. It provides an overview

¹ D4.1 Dataset for training SSH LLMs - GRAPHIA project report, not for public dissemination.

of the deployment infrastructure, the foundation models available within GRAPHIA, the LLM-based services built on them, and the mechanisms by which these capabilities are exposed to users. Detailed technical documentation of individual services is maintained separately by the respective service owners and referenced where appropriate.

1.2. Structure of the Document

The remainder of this document is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the deployment infrastructure supporting SSH LLM services. Section 3 provides an overview of the deployed LLM models and related services, describing their role within GRAPHIA, deployment characteristics, and access mechanisms. Finally, Section 4 summarises the main findings of this deliverable and discusses sustainability considerations and ethical aspects related to the operation of LLM services within the GRAPHIA ecosystem.

2. Deployment Infrastructure

The deployment infrastructure supporting GRAPHIA AI services is organised into three complementary execution environments, each addressing different functional requirements. The OKD platform provides the primary environment for deploying containerised applications and microservices, enabling standardised lifecycle management, scalability, and separation between development and production workloads. High Performance Computing (HPC) resources complement the OKD environment by providing access to specialised computational infrastructure for GPU-intensive LLM inference, experimentation, and future model adaptation. Finally, dedicated virtual machines provide an agile experimentation layer that supports rapid prototyping and iterative validation of novel services, enabling technical exploration without affecting production-ready environments.

This layered approach enables GRAPHIA to balance operational stability with computational flexibility. User-facing services can be deployed and maintained within OKD, while demanding AI workloads can leverage HPC resources transparently when required. In addition, a dedicated virtual machine environment is maintained as a sandbox for rapid prototyping, exploratory experiments, and early-stage validation of new services before they are transitioned to more managed environments. As these resources are intended for temporary development activities rather than

operational service deployment, they are not discussed further in this deliverable. The resulting infrastructure provides a practical foundation for the deployment and operation of the SSH-oriented LLM services described in the following sections.

Figure 1. Architecture of the GRAPHIA computing infrastructure deployed at PCSS, comprising OKD environments, HPC resources, and virtual machines

Unlike other OKD components, the LLM4SSH services remain hosted within the original graphia-app1-staging project. This environment was established during the initial phase of the GRAPHIA project, when activities focused primarily on the preparation of SSH training datasets, experimentation with large language models, and the deployment of computationally demanding LLM workloads. At that stage, the overall organisation of the GRAPHIA computing infrastructure had not yet been defined.

As the LLM4SSH environment required substantial GPU allocations to support model training and inference activities, no separate production namespace was provisioned at a later stage. Instead, the deployed services underwent operational validation and were assessed against the applicable production readiness criteria. Following successful validation, the services hosted within *graphia-app1-staging* were operated as production services while remaining deployed in the original environment.

While Figure 1 presents the infrastructure resources allocated at the time of writing, the architecture remains extensible and may be expanded with additional OKD, HPC, or virtual-machine resources as new requirements emerge during the project.

2.1. OKD Environment

Description

OKD is a platform for building and deploying containerised applications. It has been designed to enable applications and the data centres that host them to scale from just a few machines and applications to thousands of machines serving millions of customers.

The OKD platform is, in effect, an extension of the open-source Kubernetes (K8s) concept, enhanced with additional tools, particularly those that facilitate project management. This project is managed by Red Hat on a community-driven basis. OKD is an open-source and free platform. On the other hand, Red Hat offers a paid platform called OpenShift, which is based on OKD; however, Red Hat provides technical support and security certifications for the platform. This is important for enterprise products. At the kernel of the solution is Kubernetes, as mentioned. Because of this software, we decided to use the OKD platform.

Kubernetes is the engine and the foundation. A tool developed primarily by Google (using the Go programming language) that is responsible for running, scaling, and networking containers. It is the de facto standard for container orchestration. Although container images and the containers deployed from them are fundamental building blocks of modern application development, deploying them at scale requires a reliable and flexible distribution system. Kubernetes provides a set of tools. These enable the deployment, maintenance, and scaling of software. The software is deployed within containers. As a result, on the one hand, Kubernetes can be highly

flexible and tailored to specific needs. On the other hand, managing the software and scaling in particular is straightforward. As a result, with relatively little effort, it is possible to achieve good software performance, which depends primarily on the available resources rather than labour-intensive human activities.

This platform allows users to manage and run OCI-compatible² container images, such as Docker or CRI-O.

Architecture

Kubernetes manages different types of objects. The most important are:

- A Pod: is an abstraction that groups a set of containers; each of the containers represents a piece of software containerised within an image; usually, each container performs a single function;
- A Service is another abstraction; it exposes Pods that perform the functions necessary to provide a specific capability to the user; additionally, it performs load balancing to distribute the traffic.
- Volumes represent those Kubernetes components that provide long-term data storage (standard file systems in Pods are of an ephemeral nature).
- Namespaces represent tenants to separate workloads and allow granulation of permissions; components can be organised according to user-defined rules; for example, they enable a single Kubernetes platform to host development, testing, and production environments.
- Secrets are a Kubernetes feature that allows you to store and manage elements critical to the security of the information being processed. These include keys, passwords, access tokens, etc.

The container runtime has evolved over time. Early versions of OpenShift used Docker as the container runtime, whereas modern releases use CRI-O. Regardless of the runtime, OpenShift supports industry-standard OCI-compliant container images, so images built with Docker, Podman, Buildah, and other OCI-compatible tools can be run without modification.

² OCI (Open Container Initiative) is an industry initiative that defines open specifications for container images and runtimes, enabling interoperability between different container technologies such as Docker and CRI-O.

The second component, alongside OKD, is the registry system in which images are stored. These two environments work together to deliver the services designed by the developers. A diagram below presents the architecture of OKD:

525-OpenShift-arch-012025

Figure 2: Architecture of OKD, originally sourced from (“Official OKD Documentation,” accessed: 15/06/2026)

OKD lifecycle

The basic operations performed in the OKD cluster can be divided into two groups – those related to managing the cluster:

- Creating an OKD cluster
- Managing the cluster

and those relating to the applications being run:

- Creating and deploying applications
- Scaling applications

The diagram below illustrates the basic life cycle of an OKD

Figure 3: OKD Lifecycle, originally sourced from (“Official OKD Documentation,” accessed: 15/06/2026)

Within GRAPHIA, the OKD platform is used as the primary environment for deploying and operating containerised services. While the cluster itself is provisioned and maintained by platform administrators, GRAPHIA developers focus on deploying, configuring, and managing application workloads throughout their operational lifecycle.

OKD in GRAPHIA

In the GRAPHIA Project, we use a specific implementation of the Kubernetes environment, version 1.33, running on the OKD platform 4.20. OKD software (since August 2018) is based on Kubernetes and CRI-O and builds on this platform to provide application lifecycle management functions and DevOps tools.

1. The broad scope of the project.

The GRAPHIA project involves a wide range of software (both existing and new). This software is not homogeneous. This means the system must provide a platform that enables consistent implementation. It is extremely important that the implemented software operates securely and that the implementation process itself is straightforward.

2. Performance

The platform must offer sufficient computational power. This can be achieved via horizontal and vertical scaling offered by OKD.

The scaling can be based on different factors, for instance, manual, on demand, or based on metrics like CPU (vCPU), GPU or memory utilisation.

3. Flexible GPU access

Many components require access to the graphics processing unit (GPU). As this is an expensive resource, the platform should not only facilitate its use but also share this resource among various system components.

4. Convenient security management

This covers both the security of project-related communications (e.g., secrets) and the network security of services offered on the internet (e.g., firewalls)

Monitoring and observability

The operation of services deployed on OKD is supported by the monitoring and observability mechanisms provided by the platform itself. These mechanisms allow service owners and platform administrators to monitor the health and status of deployed workloads, verify resource consumption, and identify operational issues affecting service availability.

Application logs are available through the platform logging facilities and can be used for troubleshooting and operational diagnostics. In addition, externally exposed LLM4SSH services are continuously monitored through an independent uptime monitoring platform operated by ODOMA, providing an external perspective on service availability and endpoint accessibility.

Production readiness criteria for OKD-hosted services

The production readiness of services deployed on the OKD platform is assessed according to the operational procedures and recommendations maintained by the PCSS PaaS team. The evaluation is based on the OKD Production Readiness

Checklist³ available to platform users and aims to ensure that deployed services can be operated reliably within the GRAPHIA ecosystem.

The checklist addresses several operational domains, including:

- **Availability and resilience**
 - appropriate replication or high-availability mechanisms,
 - measures to minimise service disruption during maintenance activities,
 - validation of service behaviour under representative workloads.
- **Deployment and scheduling**
 - reproducible deployment configurations,
 - explicit versioning of container images and dependencies,
 - appropriate resource requests and limits,
 - deployment strategies supporting controlled service updates.
- **Storage and backup**
 - backup procedures for persistent data,
 - verification of recovery mechanisms where applicable,
 - consideration of external data sources and their protection requirements.
- **Monitoring and observability**
 - health monitoring mechanisms,
 - collection and retention of application logs,
 - alerting and operational visibility through relevant metrics.
- **Infrastructure as Code**
 - version-controlled deployment definitions,
 - automated or documented deployment procedures,
 - traceability of configuration changes.
- **Operational management**
 - clearly defined service ownership,
 - established responsibilities for maintenance and incident handling.

The production readiness of OKD-hosted services is achieved through a combination of platform capabilities and service-level operational practices. The OKD environment provides a managed deployment platform with built-in mechanisms for resource management, networking, monitoring, logging, security, and controlled

³ More details about that can be found here: (“PCSS OKD Production Readiness Checklist” <https://docs.psnc.pl/spaces/PAAS/pages/309925780/Production+readiness+checklist>)

application lifecycle management. At the same time, service owners are responsible for the application-specific aspects of production readiness, including functional validation, configuration management, version control of deployment artefacts, service maintenance, and user-facing documentation.

Operational readiness is further supported by external service availability monitoring operated by ODOMA, which continuously verifies the accessibility of user-facing endpoints from outside the deployment environment.

The OKD-hosted services described in this deliverable satisfy the production readiness requirements outlined above and are currently operated as production services within GRAPHIA.

2.2. HPC Environment

The execution of computationally demanding AI workloads within GRAPHIA is supported by the High Performance Computing ⁴ infrastructure operated by PCSS. The HPC environment complements the OKD-based deployment platform by providing the computational resources required for large language model (LLM) inference, experimentation, and model adaptation.

The current HPC infrastructure is based on the Eagle ecosystem, which today consists primarily of the Altair and Proxima partitions. Altair provides a large-scale CPU-oriented environment for general scientific computing, while Proxima has been specifically designed for AI and accelerator-intensive workloads, offering NVIDIA H100 GPU nodes interconnected through a high-bandwidth InfiniBand NDR network.

The infrastructure provides:

- high-performance GPU resources for LLM execution and fine-tuning,
- scalable CPU resources for auxiliary processing tasks,
- distributed high-performance storage based on Lustre,
- integration with external services through high-speed networking,
- workload orchestration through the SLURM resource manager.

⁴ Details about the PCSS High Performance Computing (HPC) can be found in an official documentation here: (“PCSS HPC Official Documentation,”).

A detailed technical specification of the PCSS HPC infrastructure is publicly available through the PCSS HPC documentation portal and has already been presented in Deliverable D4.1 (*Datasets for training SSH LLMs*). Therefore, only those aspects directly relevant to the deployment and operation of SSH LLM services are discussed in this document.

Inference Execution and Integration

Within GRAPHIA, deployed AI models are exposed as a managed inference service. Although the models are executed internally as standard SLURM (Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management) jobs on the HPC infrastructure. Each job runs a single vLLM⁵ inference server instance hosting one model, executed within a Singularity container. Model weights are loaded from Lustre shared storage at job startup, in either native precision (BF16/FP16) or quantised format depending on model requirements. Jobs are submitted and managed manually by PCSS administrators. Each job runs for a maximum of 7 days, after which it is automatically resubmitted by SLURM, ensuring continuous service availability with minimal interruption. External users interact with them through the GRAPHIA LLM Gateway and the LiteLLM service layer.

This architecture abstracts the complexity of the underlying HPC environment. From the user perspective, access is provided through standard API endpoints, while scheduling, resource allocation, and GPU management remain transparent operational concerns handled by the PCSS infrastructure.

The vLLM interface implements PagedAttention - a memory management mechanism that handles the KV-cache (key-value tensors computed by attention layers during inference) using paged allocation rather than contiguous per-request memory blocks. This eliminates memory fragmentation and enables efficient GPU memory utilisation under concurrent load, resulting in higher request throughput compared to naive inference implementations.

Each vLLM instance exposes an OpenAI-compatible HTTP API on a host port of the assigned compute node, reachable within the internal cluster network. These endpoints are registered with the LiteLLM gateway, which provides unified access,

⁵ Each job runs a single vLLM (Virtual Large Language Model) inference server, an open-source high-performance serving framework for large language models, hosting one model and executed within a Singularity container.

request routing, load balancing across parallel instances of the same model, and fallback handling in case of endpoint unavailability. From the perspective of upstream services and users, the underlying HPC infrastructure remains fully transparent.

Figure 4: HPC Architecture

Model Training and Fine-tuning

In addition to providing access to pre-deployed models, the infrastructure supports training and fine-tuning. These workloads require direct access to the HPC environment. They are executed as regular SLURM jobs, either through secure shell access or via interactive web-based environments integrated with machine learning toolchains such as MLflow.

The GRAPHIA project therefore benefits from two complementary operational services:

- an HPC service dedicated to computational workloads,
- a managed AI inference service exposing deployed LLMs through a unified API layer.

Scalability and Resource Allocation

The deployment topology for each model is determined by its parameter count and GPU memory requirements. Three deployment classes are used in practice:

- **Single-GPU** - for models whose weights and KV-cache fit within a single H100 GPU.
- **Multi-GPU, single-node** - tensor parallelism across multiple GPUs within one Proxima node for medium-sized models.
- **Multi-node** - pipeline parallelism across two or three Proxima nodes, connected via Infiniband, for the largest models.

GPU resources are exclusively allocated per SLURM job, preventing contention between concurrently running model instances.

Monitoring and observability

The HPC infrastructure provides operational monitoring capabilities supporting both infrastructure administrators and service operators. Resource utilisation metrics, including CPU, memory, storage, and GPU consumption, are collected through the HPC monitoring stack. These mechanisms provide visibility into node health, workload execution, and accelerator utilisation.

Service execution is additionally monitored through SLURM job management facilities, which provide information about job status, execution history, resource allocation, and failures. Logs generated by inference services are retained for troubleshooting and operational diagnostics. Together, these mechanisms support the reliable operation of HPC-hosted LLM services and facilitate performance analysis and capacity planning.

Inference workloads are monitored through an observability platform based on Prometheus and Grafana. The vLLM inference engine exposes metrics including request throughput, generation latency, and request queue length, which are visualised through operational dashboards and used for continuous service

monitoring. For example, Figure 5 presents the distribution of requests across deployed LLM models over time.

Figure 5: Distribution of requests across deployed LLM models over time

In addition to infrastructure-level monitoring, token-level usage statistics are collected by the LiteLLM gateway and stored in OpenSearch. These data are exposed through the users and services portal, providing visibility into resource consumption and supporting quota enforcement. Requests originating from users or services that exceed their allocated quota can be restricted at the gateway level.

Input data submitted to the models are not retained beyond the lifetime of an individual inference request, in accordance with the zero-retention policy applied to HPC inference workloads.

Production readiness criteria for HPC-hosted services

The production readiness of HPC-hosted services differs from that of OKD-hosted services due to the operational model of the underlying infrastructure. While OKD services are deployed and managed directly by service owners, HPC-based services rely on a centrally operated environment administered by the PCSS HPC team.

For this reason, a large part of the production readiness process is embedded within the standard HPC operational procedures. Services intended for operational use within GRAPHIA are deployed using established HPC practices that ensure the reliability and maintainability of the underlying infrastructure. An HPC-hosted service may be considered production-ready when the following conditions are met:

- **Operational ownership**
 - A responsible partner and operational contact have been identified.
 - Incident handling responsibilities are clearly defined.
- **Deployment reproducibility**
 - The service deployment procedure is documented.
 - Model versions, dependencies, and execution environments are explicitly specified.
 - Deployment artefacts (e.g. containers, scripts, configuration files) are maintained under version control.
- **Validation and testing**
 - The service has undergone functional validation.
 - Representative inference workloads have been tested.
 - Where applicable, stress or scalability tests have been performed.
- **Monitoring and observability**
 - Service execution can be monitored through available HPC mechanisms.
 - Logs are collected and retained for troubleshooting purposes.
 - Basic operational metrics (e.g. request failures, response times, GPU utilisation) are available.
- **Resource allocation**
 - Appropriate computational resources have been assigned and validated.
 - GPU, storage, and scheduling requirements are documented.
 - Service-level expectations regarding availability and performance are defined.
- **Data and model management**
 - Model artefacts and configuration files are stored in controlled locations.
 - Procedures exist for updating models and rolling back to previous versions if necessary.

- Any datasets required for operation comply with applicable governance requirements.
- **User access**
 - The intended user group and access mechanisms are defined.
 - Authentication and authorisation procedures are documented.
 - User-facing documentation is available.

The criteria listed above are fulfilled through a combination of established HPC operational procedures and responsibilities assigned to the service owners. The HPC infrastructure and its operational processes provide the foundations for service deployment, resource allocation, monitoring, logging, security, and operational maintenance. Service owners remain responsible for validating the functional suitability of the services, defining their intended use, maintaining service-specific documentation, and ensuring that the deployed models meet the requirements of their target use cases. Based on the criteria outlined above, all HPC-hosted services described in this deliverable are considered production-ready and are operated under standard HPC service procedures.

3. LLM4SSH models and related services: Current Deployment Status

This section provides an overview of the LLM ecosystem that was operational within GRAPHIA at the time of preparing this deliverable. The deployed components are grouped into two categories reflecting their role within the overall architecture: **LLM models for SSH** and **LLM-related services**.

The first category, **LLM models for SSH**, comprises the foundation models deployed within the GRAPHIA infrastructure. These include models selected, adapted, and, where appropriate, further trained within the activities of Task 4.1 to address the needs of the SSH community. Their development and adaptation process has been described previously in Deliverable D4.1 (Zhu and Romanello, 2026). The present deliverable focuses on their operational deployment, execution environments, and availability to GRAPHIA users and services.

The second category, **LLM-related services**, consists of software services built on top of these deployed models. These services expose AI functionalities to end users and other GRAPHIA components through dedicated interfaces and APIs, enabling integration with SSH-oriented workflows and applications.

For each deployed component, the following information is provided where applicable: its role within GRAPHIA, deployment characteristics, operational architecture, dependencies on supporting microservices, and mechanisms through which the functionality is made accessible to users. The section concludes with a summary of stress-testing activities undertaken to validate the robustness and operational readiness of the deployed services.

3.1. LLM models for SSH

Service vllm-openai-mistral-24

Service Overview

- Infrastructure type: OKD
- Deployment name: llm-openai-mistral-24
- Port: TCP/8000 → pod: 8000 (exposed externally via an OpenShift edge-TLS route, i.e. HTTPS/443)
- Endpoint: vLLM inference endpoint serving Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct; single GPU-backed replica.

Description

The service hosts

`mistralai/Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct-2506`, a 24B-parameter instruction-tuned model with a 128k-token context window, native function/tool calling, and multimodal (vision) capability. It is served through a vLLM runtime exposing an OpenAI-compatible HTTP API, started in Mistral format (`--tokenizer_mode mistral, --config-format mistral, --load-format mistral`) with automatic tool-choice enabled. Within GRAPHIA, the model is the LLM backend for the SSH Citation Index (CI) service, where it supports bibliographic reference extraction and parsing — reference segmentation and metadata-field extraction — across the

multilingual and footnote-centric publication formats characteristic of the Social Sciences and Humanities.

Service details

- **Service Owner:** ODOMA
- **Contributing Partners:** –
- **Purpose of the Service:**
 - Provides a self-hosted, OpenAI-compatible chat/completions endpoint with function-calling support, serving as the LLM backend for the GRAPHIA SSH Citation Index API. It enables LLM-based reference extraction and parsing as an alternative or complement to other tools (e.g., Grobid), targeting SSH-specific challenges (multilingual references, footnote-based citation styles, heterogeneous layouts). Hosting the model under project control keeps processed full-text content within the GRAPHIA/PCSS environment; the intended consumer is the Citation Index API service, as well as direct end users.
- **Input and Output:**
 - Accepts OpenAI-compatible chat/completions requests (system/user messages, optional tool definitions; text and, at model level, image inputs). Returns generated text and structured tool-call outputs. Request/response over HTTP, with streaming supported by vLLM.
- **Deployment Model:**
 - Deployed on OKD as a single-replica Deployment (**Recreate** update strategy). Resources: 4 vCPU, 10 GiB RAM, and one NVIDIA **MIG-7g.94gb** GPU slice (full-GPU profile; the model requires ~55 GB GPU RAM in BF16/FP16). Runtime: vLLM (**vllm/vllm-openai**), **--gpu-memory-utilization 0.98**, **--tensor-parallel-size 1**. Model weights are pulled from Hugging Face (token via Kubernetes Secret) and cached on a 100 GiB PersistentVolumeClaim; an in-memory **/dev/shm** volume is mounted for vLLM.
- **Access and Usage:**
 - Endpoint (staging):
<https://vllm-openai-mistral-24b-graphia-app1-st>

`aging.apps.bst2.paas.psnc.pl`. OpenAI-compatible API. Access is authenticated with a per-service API key (`VLLM_API_KEY`, stored as a Secret); the OpenShift route terminates TLS at the edge.

- The service is exposed via the [LiteLLM gateway](#).

Service Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0

Service overview

- Infrastructure type: OKD
- Deployment name: Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0
- Port: TCP/8080 → pod: 8080 (exposed via a NodePort service in port 30080)
- Endpoint: llama.cpp inference endpoint serving Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0; single GPU-backed replica.

Description

The service hosts `unsloth/Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0`, a 30B-parameter Mixture of experts instruction tuned code model with 3B active parameters in 8-bit quantization, served through a llama.cpp runtime exposing an OpenAI-compatible HTTP API. The server runs with flash attention, 16 threads, and a context window of 256k tokens. Within Graphia, the model serves as part of the LLM backend for the quagga-agent, where it supports code generation, completion, and analysis tasks.

Service details

- **Service Owner:** ODOMA
- **Contributing Partners:** –
- **Purpose of the Service:**
 - Provides a self-hosted, OpenAI-compatible chat/completions endpoint serving as part of the LLM backend for the GRAPHIA Quagga-Agent. It enables LLM-based code generation and analysis, leveraging the Qwen3-Coder model's code-specialised

capabilities. Hosting the model under project control keeps processed content within the GRAPHIA/PCSS environment; the intended consumer is the Quagga-Agent service, as well as direct end users who use it for code analysis tasks.

- **Input and Output:**
 - Accepts OpenAI-compatible chat/completions requests (system/user messages; text inputs). Returns generated text. Request/response over HTTP, with streaming supported by llama.cpp server.
- **Deployment Model:**
 - Deployed on OKD as a single-replica Deployment (**Recreate** update strategy). Resources: 4 vCPU, 10 GiB RAM, and two NVIDIA **MIG-3g.47gb** GPU slice (the quantized GGUF model in 8-bit quantization requires ~32 GB GPU RAM). Runtime: llama.cpp server (ghcr.io/ggml-org/llama.cpp:server-cuda-b5618), flash attention enabled, 16 threads. Model weights are pulled from Hugging Face ([unsloth/Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0](https://huggingface.co/unsloth/Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0)) via huggingface_hub with hf_transfer acceleration and cached on a PersistentVolumeClaim (quagga-llm-volume, mounted at /tmp).
- **Access and Usage:**
 - Internal endpoint (staging): quagga-llm-service.graphia-app1-staging.svc.cluster.local (accessible within the cluster only). External access via NodePort 30080 on all cluster nodes. OpenAI-compatible API.
 - The service is exposed via the [LiteLLM gateway](#).

Service qwen-embedding-deployment

Service overview

- Infrastructure type: OKD
- Deployment name: qwen-embedding-deployment
- Port: TCP/8000 -> pod: 8000

- Endpoint: Text embedding endpoint serving the Qwen3-Embedding-0.6B model; runs as a 3-replica OKD Deployment, each replica backed by a MIG GPU slice.

Description

The service exposes a text-embedding endpoint based on [Qwen/Qwen3-Embedding-0.6B](#), a compact (0.6B-parameter) multilingual embedding model supporting a 32k-token context and 1024-dimensional output vectors. It is served through a vLLM runtime providing an OpenAI-compatible HTTP API. Within GRAPHIA, the service generates dense vector representations of textual content to support semantic search and retrieval-augmented workflows over the SSH Knowledge Graph, and is consumed by the Quagga agent and other retrieval-dependent components rather than accessed directly by end users.

Service details

- **Service Owner:** ODOMA
- **Contributing Partners:** Net7 (testing of deployment)
- **Purpose of the Service:**
 - Generation of dense text embeddings for semantic similarity, retrieval, and clustering tasks. It addresses the need for vector-based retrieval over SSH content; intended users are other GRAPHIA services (programmatic consumers) rather than human end users.
- **Input and Output:**
 - Accepts one or more text strings via an OpenAI-compatible `/v1/embeddings` request (JSON, `model` + `input` fields; inputs longer than the 32k-token window must be chunked).
 - Returns 1024-dimensional embedding vectors per input. Interaction is request/response over HTTP.
- **Deployment Model:**
 - Deployed on OKD as a 3-replica deployment. Resources per replica: 4 vCPU, 8 GiB RAM, and one NVIDIA MIG `1g.12gb` GPU slice.
 - Runtime: vLLM (`vllm/vllm-openai`) with `--trust-remote-code, --max-model-len 32000,`

`--gpu-memory-utilization 0.7`. Liveness/readiness probes on `/health`.

- **Access and Usage:**
 - Endpoint (staging):
`https://qwen-embedding-route-graphia-app1-staging.apps.bst2.paas.psncl.pl`. OpenAI-compatible embeddings API. The OKD route is configured with an extended HAProxy timeout (240 s) to accommodate large embedding batches.
 - The service is exposed via the LiteLLM gateway [REF].

Service DeepSeek v3

Service overview

- Infrastructure type: HPC
- Deployment name: DeepSeek-V3.1-AWQ
- Port: -
- Endpoint: HPC LiteLLM gateway

Description

The service hosts the DeepSeek-V3.1-AWQ model deployed within the PCSS HPC infrastructure and exposed as a managed AI service for the GRAPHIA ecosystem. During deployment, several runtime configurations were evaluated to improve inference efficiency and scalability. In particular, different versions of vLLM and LMCache were investigated to enable KV-cache persistence and cache reuse in distributed multi-node settings. Although cache persistence mechanisms could successfully store KV entries, stability issues were encountered when retrieving cached data in multi-node configurations, preventing reliable use of cache offloading during the evaluation period. The deployment process therefore contributed to identifying practical limitations and compatibility considerations associated with operating very large AWQ-quantised models in HPC environments.

Service details

- **Service Owner:** PCSS
- **Contributing Partners:** Odoma (testing of deployment)

- **Purpose of the Service:**
 - Provides access to a high-capability large language model supporting experimentation and operational use within GRAPHIA. The service enables conversational interaction, information extraction, analytical tasks, and the evaluation of advanced LLM capabilities relevant to SSH applications. It is intended both for direct user interaction and for integration with higher-level GRAPHIA services.
- **Input and Output:**
 - Accepts text prompts through an OpenAI-compatible API interface and returns generated textual responses. Communication follows a request/response model and supports conversational interactions.
- **Deployment Model:**
 - The deployment relies on vLLM-based inference and multi-node execution techniques required by the size of the model.
- **Access and Usage:**
 - Access to the service is decoupled from direct access to the HPC environment, making the underlying computational infrastructure transparent to end users.
 - The service is exposed via HPC LiteLLM.

3.2. LLM-related services

Service LiteLLM

OKD Microservices

- **LiteLLM**
 - Port: TCP/4000 → pod: 4000 (exposed externally via an OpenShift edge-TLS route, i.e. HTTPS/443, at the public domain llm.graphia-ssh.eu)
 - LLM router gateway providing a unified, OpenAI-compatible entry point to all GRAPHIA-hosted model services; single replica backed by managed PostgreSQL and Redis.

Description

The service runs LiteLLM, an open-source LLM proxy/gateway that aggregates the GRAPHIA model backends behind a single OpenAI-compatible HTTP API. It is the public-facing entry point through which the other deployed services (e.g. vllm-openai-mistral-24, Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct, qwen-embedding-deployment) are exposed and consumed — each of the preceding service subsections refers to this gateway. Rather than serving a model itself, LiteLLM routes incoming requests to the appropriate upstream vLLM endpoint and adds a uniform management layer on top: virtual API-key issuance, per-key authentication and access control, usage and spend tracking, response caching, request logging, and email notifications. Model definitions are persisted in a PostgreSQL database (store_model_in_db), so backends can be added or updated at runtime through the database or the admin UI without redeploying; Redis provides a shared cache and backs the routing/rate-limiting state across proxy instances. Within GRAPHIA, LiteLLM is the single integration point against which partner services and end users develop, decoupling consumers from the individual model deployments and their network locations.

Service details

- **Service Owner:** ODOMA
- **Contributing Partners:** –
- **Purpose of the Service:**
 - Provides a single, OpenAI-compatible gateway that unifies access to all GRAPHIA SSH LLM and embedding services. It centralises authentication and authorisation (per-service/per-user virtual API keys derived from a master key), usage accounting and request logging, response caching, and routing across model backends. This decouples consuming services and end users from the underlying deployments — they target one stable endpoint and model catalogue instead of many — and gives operators a single point for key management, monitoring, and cost/usage control. Intended users are both programmatic GRAPHIA services and direct end users.
- **Input and Output:**

- Accepts OpenAI-compatible requests on the standard routes — chat/completions, embeddings, and model listing (/v1/models) — authenticated with a virtual API key. Requests are routed to the matching upstream vLLM backend; the gateway returns the backend's generated text, tool-call, or embedding output unchanged, with streaming preserved. Interaction is request/response over HTTPS.
- **Deployment Model:**
 - Deployed on OKD as a single-replica deployment using the non-root LiteLLM image (`ghcr.io/berriai/litellm-non_root:main-v1.82.3-stable`, pinned for stability). Resources: requests 2 vCPU / 4 GiB RAM, limits 4 vCPU / 8 GiB RAM; container port 4000, fronted by a NodePort Service. State is externalised to two managed services deployed via the PSNC Helm charts: a PostgreSQL instance (postgresql-simple, 5 GiB persistent volume) holding keys, model definitions, and spend/prompt logs, and a Redis instance (redis-simple, 5 GiB persistent volume, TLS-enabled) used for caching and shared routing state. Key settings include routing_strategy simple-shuffle, drop_params, a 600 s request timeout, Redis-backed caching, JSON logging, periodic background health checks (every 2 h), and SMTP-based email notifications. Secrets (master key, salt key, database and Redis passwords, SMTP password) are provided through a Kubernetes Secret.
- **Access and Usage:**
 - Endpoint (production): `https://llm.graphia-ssh.eu`. OpenAI-compatible API, consumable with the standard OpenAI client by setting `base_url` to the gateway and supplying a virtual API key (`GRAPHIA_API_KEY`). The OpenShift route terminates TLS at the edge (Let's Encrypt⁶ certificate via cert-manager) and redirects insecure traffic. The same domain serves the LiteLLM admin UI for key and model management.

⁶ Let's Encrypt is a publicly trusted certificate authority providing free, automatically issued TLS certificates for securing HTTPS endpoints (see: <https://letsencrypt.org/>).

- Technical Documentation:
https://docs.litellm.ai/docs/simple_proxy

Service Quagga agent

OKD Microservices

- `quagga-agent-api` — orchestration of agent workflows
- `quagga-agent-webui` — OpenWebUI-based user interface

Description

Quagga agent is a user-facing conversational service that lets researchers query the SSH Knowledge Graph in natural language, combining large language models with retrieval and reasoning to support exploratory search, question answering, and user-guided knowledge discovery. It is implemented as a set of cooperating microservices on OKD: an agent API orchestrating the workflow, a web UI, a dedicated LLM inference backend, and a crowdsourcing/evaluation component for knowledge-graph question answering (KGQA).

Service details

- **Service Owner:** ODOMA
- **Contributing Partners:** –
- **Purpose of the Service:**
 - Provides conversational, natural-language access to KGs, lowering the barrier to querying complex graph structures. It supports exploratory search, question answering, and guided knowledge discovery; intended users are SSH researchers interacting via the web UI.
- **Input and Output:**
 - Accepts natural-language questions through the web UI / agent API. Returns natural-language answers grounded in the knowledge graph and the corresponding SPARQL query.
- **Deployment Model:**
 - Deployed on OKD; the orchestration and UI components rely on container orchestration for scalability and lifecycle management. It uses LLMs deployed on OKD and HPC

infrastructures such as GLM 5.1 and Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct (see description above).

- **Access and Usage:**

- User interface:

<https://quagga-agent.graphia-ssh.eu>. An API endpoint compatible with the OpenAI API is being finalised and will be available (under authentication) to allow using the Quagga agent as a component in GRAPHIA's federated gateway.

3.3. Performance and stress testing

In addition to the deployment activities described above, selected LLM-based services underwent operational evaluation and stress testing activities conducted by Net7, with support from other GRAPHIA partners. The objective of these tests was to assess the responsiveness, scalability, and robustness of the deployed conversational workflows under realistic usage scenarios.

The evaluation focused on the GoTriple chatbot architecture and compared the behaviour of several models, including GPT-4.1-mini, GPT-5, and DeepSeek, under different workloads and retrieval settings. The tests considered scenarios involving varying numbers of concurrent users, the use of retrieved documents as additional context, and multi-turn conversations.

The results highlighted significant differences in operational characteristics between the evaluated models. GPT-4.1-mini consistently demonstrated low response latency across the tested workloads, whereas DeepSeek exhibited substantially longer response times when processing large contextual inputs. At the same time, the experiments showed that deployment-level optimisations, such as warm KV cache mechanisms, could significantly improve the responsiveness of DeepSeek-based conversational services. For example, DeepSeek response times under a 10-user workload decreased from approximately four minutes to around 77 seconds when warm KV cache mechanisms were applied, illustrating the impact of deployment-level optimisations on service performance.

These activities provided valuable feedback for refining deployment configurations and informed decisions regarding the operational use of LLM services within GRAPHIA. A detailed description of the testing methodology and benchmark results is available in the dedicated stress-testing report prepared for the project. The report documents performance measurements collected under workloads of up to 20 concurrent users and includes analyses of response times and time-to-first-token metrics.

3.4. Production-readiness status

The production readiness mechanisms summarised above reflect the environment-specific criteria described in Sections 2.1 and 2.2. OKD services were validated against the OKD production readiness checklist, while HPC-hosted services follow the operational procedures established for managed HPC AI services at PCSS. All LLM4SSH services are additionally covered by independent external uptime monitoring operated by ODOMA.

Service name	Infrastructure type	Owner	Purpose	Production Status	Production readiness mechanism
Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct	OKD	ODOMA	Support for the SSH Citation Index; bibliographic reference extraction and parsing	Production-ready	OKD checklist; external uptime monitoring
Qwen3-Coder-30B-A3B-Instruct-Q8_0	OKD	ODOMA	LLM backend for Quagga-Agent supporting natural language queries processing, code generation and analysis	Production-ready	OKD checklist; external uptime monitoring
Qwen3-Embedding-0.6B	OKD	ODOMA	Embedding generation for semantic retrieval and retrieval-augmented workflows	Production-ready	OKD checklist; external uptime monitoring
DeepSeek-V3.1-AWQ	HPC	PCSS	General-purpose LLM access, experimentation, and advanced SSH-oriented AI workflows	Production-ready	HPC provisioning procedures; external uptime monitoring

Table 2.1: Summary of the LLM services deployed within GRAPHIA and the mechanisms supporting their production readiness.

4. Conclusions

4.1. Integration and Sustainability

Within GRAPHIA, WP4 focuses on Artificial Intelligence solutions supporting the SSH Knowledge Graph ecosystem, including conversational access to knowledge graphs, AI-assisted querying, and LLM-based interaction services. The services described in this deliverable operate in conjunction with components developed in other work packages, in particular the SSH Knowledge Graph infrastructure developed within WP2.

The deployment infrastructure operated by PCSS provides the operational layer required to host, expose, monitor, and scale AI services developed within WP4. Through the GRAPHIA LLM Gateway, these services integrate with other GRAPHIA components, including the GoTriple Knowledge Graph, Federated Gateway, conversational interfaces, knowledge graph question-answering workflows, and related AI-enabled services supporting SSH research activities.

This deliverable should therefore be considered complementary to the broader GRAPHIA technical architecture documentation provided in other project outputs, in particular Deliverable D2.2 *Technical Architecture*. While D2.2 describes the overall system architecture, this deliverable documents the deployment and operational aspects of the SSH LLM services available at the time of submission.

The deployed environment has been designed to support the continued evolution of the GRAPHIA AI ecosystem. Operational procedures, public technical documentation, and repository references provide the basis for maintaining, extending, and integrating these services throughout the project lifetime.

4.2 Ethical and legal aspects

The services described in this deliverable are deployed as technical components supporting the GRAPHIA ecosystem. Ethical, legal, and regulatory aspects related to the use of AI technologies are addressed within the broader governance framework of the project and are subject to further activities carried out in other work packages.

From an operational perspective, the deployment follows applicable institutional policies and takes into account the evolving European regulatory landscape, including

requirements stemming from the AI Act and the Data Act where relevant. The deployed infrastructure provides mechanisms supporting controlled access, authentication, logging, and service management.

Any future adaptations required to ensure compliance with emerging legal obligations will be addressed as part of the evolution of the GRAPHIA services.

4.3 Final Remarks

This deliverable documented the deployment of SSH-oriented LLM services within GRAPHIA, including the supporting infrastructure, deployed services, and access mechanisms. The presented environment provides the operational foundation for AI-enabled functionalities developed in WP4 and will continue to evolve throughout the project lifetime.

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Appendix A. Computing Infrastructure Resources Allocated to LLM4SSH Services

Service name	vCPU	vGPU [H100-MIG]	vRAM [GB]	Storage [GB]
quagga-llm-deployment	4	1	10	442
vllm-openai-mistral-24b	4	1	10	100
qwen-embedding-deployment	4	1	8	10

Table A.1: LLM4SSH resources allocated on OKD cluster bst2.

Service name	vCPU [alloc. hours]	vGPU [alloc. hours]	vRAM [TB]	Storage [TB]	Tokens [used]
DeepSeek-V3.1-A WQ	100 000	35 000	2	50	290 634 843

Table A.2: LLM4SSH resources allocated on HPC infrastructure.